

Not all troubles come from toxins: a list of non-toxic animal killer microalgae

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) encompass a wide range of events caused by diverse microalgae that can affect human and animal health, ecosystems, and seafood security and have economic consequences. Given the variety of targets and causative organisms, it is unsurprising that the mechanisms of impact differ among HAB types. Based on affected resources and mechanisms, HABs can be roughly subdivided into four categories (Table 1).

Regarding human health, microalgal toxins may act directly through contact or aerosol exposure, but more commonly they accumulate in seafood and can cause harm even at low cellular concentrations (Table 1A). The responsible organisms are generally well known, and include several diatoms, dinoflagellates and cyanobacteria. Different mechanisms of action and human syndromes have been identified. Fortunately, fatal cases are limited because monitoring of phytoplankton and shellfish toxicity in harvesting areas is generally mandatory. However, toxin concentrations in seafood exceeding regulatory limits often result in temporary harvesting

ban, with consequent economic losses for the shellfish industry. Additionally, unregulated seafood consumption represents a risk in areas where toxic species proliferate.

Of a different nature are toxic events causing mass mortalities or injuries to marine organisms, including pen fish, cultivated bivalves and wild fauna (Table 1B). Several microalgae producing bioactive extracellular compounds affecting animal health—such as ichthyotoxins, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and haemolysins—have been documented [see 1 for review]. These organisms mostly belong to dinoflagellates but also to other phototrophic flagellates (e.g., raphidophytes and dictyochophytes). Their toxins are distinct from those affecting human health, though in some cases microalgae toxic to humans can also harm marine animals or impair their reproductive ability [2–4].

Both types of toxic microalgae mentioned above (ca. 270 species) are listed in the IOC- UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae [5], a catalogue providing taxonomic, toxicological, morphological, and molecular information for each potentially toxic species. The list was initiated in the 1990s, on the recommendation of the IOC-FAO Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (IPHAB) to provide a unified database supporting research and monitoring. An editorial panel of taxonomy experts supervises and periodically updates the list [6]. A recent improvement added 44 cyanobacteria to the list, which initially focused only on marine species.

However, microalgae can also cause damage without producing toxins. Injuries or mortality of wild and cultivated marine fauna have frequently been associated with blooms of organisms not known to produce toxins (Table 1C), while seawater discolouration, mucilage, foams and/or unpleasant odours have caused problems in areas used for tourism and recreation (Table 1D). A comprehensive list of these non-toxic yet harmful microalgae has long been requested by the scientific and management communities but has been challenging to compile. Non-toxic taxa are part of the normal microflora, with harmful effects only occurring under specific conditions. While toxic species can be rapidly identified through chemical and morphological analyses, pinpointing the causative non-toxic species can be difficult, particularly in multispecies blooms. Additionally, the boundaries of such a list are uncertain because any microalga reaching high abundance can potentially harm marine life [7].

Acknowledging these caveats and recognizing the importance of identifying potentially harmful non-toxic species, we prepared a preliminary list based on documented cases from the Harmful Algae Event Database (HAEDAT, <https://haedat.iode.org/>) and peer-reviewed literature. The compilation was organized in two steps. The first step addressed non-toxic species associated with occasional or recurrent impacts on marine fauna (Table 1C). By design, toxic species were excluded even if other mechanisms of impact were involved.

Among 913 HAEDAT-reported animal mortality or impairment events (as of October 2025), 142 were linked to 37 taxa not known to produce toxins. Additional cases from reviews [e.g.,

Table 1. Schematic subdivision of HABs based on their impacts. Not all types of impacts are covered, and boundaries among these categories are not sharply defined. Some human toxins (A) can also affect animals (B), while many toxic species (A and B) can damage animals via mechanisms other than their known toxins (C), e.g., oxygen depletion, or produce discolourations or mucilage, impacting tourism (D). Toxic species are recorded in the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Microalgae [5], whereas the new list presented here concerns C-type species [9]. A list of species involved in D-type HABs is in preparation.

<p>A. Toxic to humans</p> <p>Toxins accumulate in seafood or irritate the skin or respiratory system</p> <p>Impacts on human health and aquaculture</p> <p>Examples: <i>Alexandrium</i> spp., <i>Dinophysis</i> spp., <i>Prorocentrum</i> spp., <i>Pseudo-nitzschia</i> spp., cyanobacteria spp.</p>	<p>B. Toxic to marine fauna</p> <p>Ichthyotoxins and other bioactive compounds damage tissues</p> <p>Impacts on the health of wild and cultured marine animals</p> <p>Examples: <i>Karenia</i> spp., <i>Heterocapsa</i> spp., <i>Margalefidinium</i> spp., <i>Chattonella</i> spp., <i>Chrysochromulina</i> spp.</p>
<p>C. Harm to marine fauna with no toxins</p> <p>Physical damage to gills via spines or mucus, oxygen depletion, or starvation</p> <p>Impacts on the health of wild and cultured marine animals</p> <p>Examples: <i>Noctiluca scintillans</i>, <i>Chaetoceros</i> spp., <i>Octactis</i> spp., <i>Triplos</i> spp., <i>Aureococcus anophagefferens</i></p>	<p>D. Harm to human activities</p> <p>Discolourations, mucilage, foams, and unpleasant odours</p> <p>Impacts on tourism, recreational, and commercial activities</p> <p>Examples: <i>Gonyaulax fragilis</i>, <i>Thalassiosira mala</i></p>

8] or peer-reviewed papers involved 30 more taxa [9]. To date, 25 diatoms, 31 dinoflagellates, four dictyochophyceans, two pelagophyceans, one cryptophycean, one raphidophycean, two chlorophytes, and the mixotrophic ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* (Fig. 1) are included in the new list on the website of the IOC-UNESCO Taxonomic Reference List of Harmful Algae, in the section 'Harmful non-toxic' species (<https://www.marinespecies.org/hab/nontoxic.php>). Species names in the list are updated according to the current nomenclature and linked to their respective WoRMS pages [10]. A downloadable Excel file summarises 120 documented cases supporting taxa inclusion, including 56 verified HAEDAT events and additional literature reports. For each case, the file provides location, time, impact, literature or HAEDAT reference, and a quality flag evaluating identification methods. Multiple events for some species are listed to indicate spatial and temporal incidence without aiming for exhaustiveness. The list is updated periodically, and contributions from the scientific community to improve its completeness and accuracy are encouraged.

An analysis of 210 HAEDAT and literature records (Fig. 2) shows that the dinoflagellate *Noctiluca scintillans* is the taxon most frequently associated with non-toxic harmful events (16% of cases), involving mortality of fish — including salmon, demersal and cultured species — as well as benthic invertebrates. Reports of such impacts span globally distant regions including the Indian and Indonesian coasts (Indian Ocean), Gulf of Trieste (Mediterranean Sea), South China Sea (Pacific Ocean), and Irish and South African coasts (North East and South East Atlantic). Other frequently represented dinoflagellates include species belonging to *Prorocentrum*, *Triplos*, and *Gonyaulax* (9, 8 and 8%, respectively). Among diatoms, *Chaetoceros* with gill-damaging setae (9%) and *Skeletonema* spp. (7%) were most frequently associated with harmful events. The dictyochophyceans *Octactis* spp. and *Dictyocha* accounted for 6% of cases. The ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum*, included because of its microalgal symbiont, was involved in 7% of the cases, while the pelagophytes *Aureococcus* and *Aureoumbra* contributed 3%. Harmfulness is supported by mul-

Fig. 1. Taxonomic composition of the list of species not known to produce toxins but responsible for injuries or death in marine animals.

multiple independent events for these taxa, whereas it remains uncertain for 41 species that were associated with only a single reported event.

A second list, also based on HAEDAT and the literature, is presently in preparation and will include species producing seawater discoloration, mucilage, foams, unpleasant odours (Table 1D), and other impacts on water quality and human activities.

Mechanisms behind non-toxic animal-kills are often poorly understood. In some *Chaetoceros* species and dictyochophyceans, the spiny siliceous cell structures damage the gills of both fish

and invertebrates, leading to suffocation [11] (Fig. 3A). Gill clogging and suffocation can also result from mucus produced by some diatoms or dinoflagellates (e.g., *Thalassiosira mala* and *Gonyaulax fragilis*). In many other cases, the decay of massive blooms (e.g., *Triplos* spp., *Prorocentrum* spp., and *Noctiluca scintillans*) depletes oxygen and can generate hydrogen sulphide, causing asphyxia and poisoning in animals unable to escape (Fig. 3B). Malnutrition due to the small size of the available prey has caused growth arrest and mortality in oysters in Thau Lagoon, France [12], during massive blooms of

Fig. 2. Relative contribution of non-toxic species to harmful events affecting marine animal health, based on 210 cases reported in HAEDAT or in the literature. The ciliate *Mesodinium rubrum* is included because of its photosynthetic microalgal symbionts. The majority (61%) of the non-toxic animal-killer species are associated with only one harmful event.

Fig. 3. Examples of injuries to marine fauna caused by microalgae, with no involvement of toxic substances. (A). Gill degeneration induced by the long siliceous setae of some diatoms in the genus *Chaetoceros* [11]. (B). A massive mortality of fish in St Helena Bay, on the South African west coast, in March 1994 due to hypoxia and hydrogen sulphide development following a bloom of *Tripos furca* and *Prorocentrum micans* — Argo photograph (C). Plumage fouling in seabirds due to the high concentration of proteinaceous substances produced by a bloom of *Akashiwo sanguinea* [14].

the trebouxiophycean *Picochlorum tauri*. Peculiar cases concern the diatoms *Coscinodiscus centralis* and *C. concinnus*, which produce oily substances that fouled birds' feathers, causing death by drowning [13], and the dinoflagellate *Akashiwo sanguinea*, which releases proteinaceous substances that also caused plumage fouling [14] (Fig. 3C). However, the latter species is not included in the new list, because it is already in the main catalogue with other ichthyotoxic species.

The list of non-toxic species should be interpreted cautiously, particularly for species associated with only one or a few events. Multispecies blooms complicate the identification of causative species, and undetected toxic species may be present. In addition, the boundary between the lists of toxic and non-toxic fish killers is at times vague. Some of the species listed among the latter, e.g., the pelagophytes *Aureococcus anophagefferens* and *Aureoumbra lagunensis* and the dinoflagellate *Prorocentrum micans*, were moved from the main catalogue to the new list due to a lack of evidence of their capacity to produce toxins *de novo*. Conversely, future studies may discover the capacity to produce toxins in some taxa now considered non-toxic. Additional information, corrections and suggestions are welcome

to enhance the list, with the hope that this initial effort will stimulate the description of similar events in HAEDAT or in the literature, thus expanding the knowledge on these natural phenomena that can damage marine life.

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